

D-JRP15-FED-AMR-WP2.1

**Protocol for Feed sampling
and
Laboratory Operating Procedure (LOP)**

[Compartment 8]

**Version 1
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Protocol for Feed sampling and Laboratory Operating Procedure (LOP)

A. Description

Compilation of sampling feeds compartment and points, and further laboratory analysis, ensuring harmonization of testing procedures, which will enhance comparability of the results obtained from different regions of Europe and among compartments. Feeds to use can be of different origins and natures, e.g. imported, locally cultivated, purchased raw material, compound feed (finished feed), preserved feed, hay (cut in the field), phenocyclation (cut, pre-dried, and baled at the end). This protocol will allow answering to the different questions from the FED-AMR project.

B. Equipment and material

- Sampling stick / spear with a long split or compartments
- Sealable plastic or paper bag for 500 g sample
- Glass or plastic bottle
- Sterile scissors (to trim long material if necessary)
- Freezer and deep freezer
- Oven
- Disposable half-mask respirator approved to EN149 standard
- Laboratory gloves
- Thermostatically controlled bath
- Sieve
- Balance
- Sterile disposable wooden spatula
- Centrifuge
- Filtration system (for bacteriology of water)
- Containers for contaminated materials
- Sterile propylene flasks, 50ml
- Sterile cryotubes

C. Procedure

1. Sampling, transportation and conservation

- Three samples of feeds are collected at one time point within one-year period (Fe1, Fe2, Fe3), in each of the HOALs (Austria, Portugal, Czech Republic and Estonia) (Table: Sampling timeline by country).
- In each extraction point collect:
 - **500 ml (minimum) to 1.5 L** of liquid/wet feed samples (dry mass <85%), **or**:
 - **500g (minimum) to 1.5kg** of solid/dry (contains not more than 15 % moisture) feed.

- The sample must be taken from the package.
- Insert a sampling stick / spear into the feed to be sampled, ensuring the slot is facing down.
- Twist the spear 180° so the slot is now facing upwards.
- Withdraw spear from the feed (keeping the slot facing upwards).
- Remove stopper from the end of the spear.
- Open the sealable bag, or glass or plastic bottle and pour the feed in. If the feed has any moisture it might be collected in paper bags.
- Repeat until a 500 ml to 1.5 L or 0.5Kg - 1.5kg sample has been collected. When taking samples ensure that the spear is inserted in different areas and to different depths of the feed to give a representative sample.
- The size of the sampled portion must be such that each of its constituent parts can be sampled; thus, the minimum number of packages to be sampled for Packaged feed (or for Liquid or Semi-liquid feed) are **4 packages** whether the Packages have more than 1 kg or not exceeding 1 kg (1 L).
- Seal the bag or bottle that only should contain sample from 1 package (only in the laboratory the feed from different packages will be mixed to constitute the composite sample).
- Sample containers should be suitable for preserving the sample integrity avoiding any changes or effects from moisture, temperature or light. The sample container should be sterile, of suitable size to allow storage of sufficient sample to complete all determinations required and there should be some air space left once filled (in order to avoid leakage and to allow effective mixing prior to sampling for all tests required in the laboratory). The container should have a securely fitting lid and should be uniquely identified with a sample identifier on the container and not the lid. As samples will be also examined microbiologically it should be handled under sterile conditions to preserve the microbiological load.
- Transportation of the samples to the laboratory shall ensure that they are kept under conditions which will minimize any alteration in the microorganisms present.
- Identify samples clearly and completely, and record the sample information.
- Storage conditions should be cautious as it alters composition, matrix interactions, chemical and/or enzymatic activity, thus should be followed the conservation indicated (that is **0°C to 5°C**).
- Testing shall begin on the day of receipt of samples or on the first working day afterwards (to avoid the loss of eDNA), which allows the method to be completed in accordance with the respective protocol.
- If exceptionally, testing is not to begin on the day of receipt, the samples must be stored in accordance with the appropriate protocol (0° to 5°C) in the dark.
- If samples have been refrigerated before testing they should be removed to room temperature (18-21°C) for a minimum of 1 hour prior to the start of the procedure.

- Samples should be stored in such a way that no cross contamination can occur with other diagnostic samples.
- All the steps for sample preparation should be done rather quickly, under convenient and very clean conditions so there could be no degradation of sensitive analytes, no contaminations and no oxidation process due to influences of too high temperatures, daylight, air or from residues of apparatus used or from samples prepared before or simultaneously.
- Stability of parameters in this context refers only to influences of sample preparation to them like e.g. intensive grinding:
 - Trace elements (e.g. Cu, Zn, Mn, Fe, Se, Co) and heavy metals (e.g. As, Pb, Cd, Hg) are considered stable parameters.
 - DNA, drugs, antibiotics, pesticides, yeasts, bacteria are considered unstable parameters, being sensitive to temperature and dryness (degradation / change).
- Milling / grinding of materials to mechanically reduce particle size, which is accomplished by shearing, impacting and attrition using various mills, should only be considered by WP4.7., if necessary, and not at this stage.

2. Sample preparation procedure

2a. *Testing portion*

- The laboratory receives samples that has not been damaged or changed during transport and storage, and corresponds to about ~0.5 kg-1.5 kg (collected before into different bags/bottles) x 3 feed samples (that might be from different natures), which will ensure the representativeness of the batch of product.
- Feeds may be solid, semi-solid/wet (contains not more than 15 % moisture) and **liquid**. However, regarding the aims of the project, which also includes the analysis of microorganisms and DNA, namely eDNA, it will not be possible to dry and/or warming samples.
- As such, they have to be treated as crops, even if semi-solid/wet and liquid, as follows:
 - For **solid and semi-solid** samples, original parts are broken into smaller parts and blended to make them more uniform in texture and consistency, and to obtain a satisfactory sized sub-sample.
 - **Long material**, such as hay, may be cut using sterile scissors to a more appropriate length if required.
 - For **fine samples**, coarse samples, grass or cereal silage samples, **semi-solid and liquid samples** the sample must be well mixed using a sterile palate knife, spoon or stirring rod before sub sampling and the required portion removed using a sterile spatula or spoon and placed in a sterile container or sterile foil which is suitably identified.
- Place the **riffled, unground sample** in a sterile laboratory labeled sample bottle (or bag, etc) avoiding cross contamination; and place the other portion(s) of unground sample back in a

sample bag to be retained. Label each container (bag, bottle, etc.) with a matching identification number (FED-AMR code).

2b. Composite sample

- For each of the 3 samples consider that: the “test sample” — i.e. the (sub-)sample prepared from the laboratory sample and from which test portions will be taken — “will be a composite sample”.
- As the **composite sample** used must be representative of the whole sample submitted, a small fraction should be taken from that large volume received, in such a way that the determinations will represent the mean value of the characteristic of the entire sample and taking into account the determinations to be made; thus, an equal portion from each part of the packages (in each of the samples) is weighted, having at the end **at least 500 g** from each of the 3 feed sample.
- From this composite sample with 500 g (1 pool for all packages) (Figure 1):
 - weight 2.75 g (in triplicate) to be used in 3 DNA extractions for metagenomics (WP2);
 - weight 2.75 g for qPCR (2.5 g for eDNA and 0.25 g for total DNA);
 - weight 1 g \pm 0.1 g of solid feeds, or 5 ml of liquid feeds [see (LOP) Protocol for Microbiology: culture and identification of *Escherichia coli*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Salmonella spp*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Enterococcus faecium/faecalis*];
 - weight 100 g to be used in quantification (WP4.7); to stop the degradation (as they get mouldy very quickly and unusable). If this portion notice any moisture it should be dried in an oven at low temp (60°C) until constant weight; once they are dry they can be kept in plastic bags for storage or transport (if a freeze drier even is used, it is better); after drying the sample should have more than 50 g (up \approx 100 g). If the laboratory do not have oven to dry feeds, could be dried at room temperature as follows: cover some trays in the laboratory with filter paper, spread the plants on them and let them dry under ambient conditions, turning them occasionally until they reached constant weight. In any case, record the weight before and after drying.
 - freeze at -80° C the remaining portion of the composite sample (about 384 g to 388 g).

Fig 1. Feed sampling (composite sample).

[*For bacteriology: 1 g ± 0.1 g of solid feeds, or 5 ml of liquid feeds].

2c. For the representativeness of sample

It is very important:

- to **use always** an equal amount of each of the samples for each types of pools;
- to be sure that a scale with at least two decimal-points are used, to ensure correct weighing of the required amounts;
- to **mix very well** the pooled sample, before using it for DNA extraction (WP2), or bacteriology (WP2), or quantification (WP4.7).

Note: The reliability and quality of the analysis of feeds depends on the accuracy of sampling. Therefore adequate care must be taken to ensure that the analytes are handled in a way that will prevent degradation and errors.

2d. Conservation in the laboratory and transport

- for Bacteriology procedures (WP2): transport and conservation at 0°C to 5°C until bacteriology be processed, which must be with pooled samples [for cultivable bacteria and MICs: to be performed in each country];
- for Quantification in WP4.7: feeds pool is transported in PET sterile bags, in dark.
- for Genomics (WP2): conservation at 0°C to 5°C until extraction of DNA; DNA extraction must be processed within the next 18h due to eDNA [using harmonized protocol; to be performed in each country].

3. Distribution and transport conditions for feed samples to ship

- For qPCR, WGS and metagenomics: if any country cannot perform it in the respective lab, extracted DNA should be shipped at -80°C to the receptor lab.
- For shipping samples by post to another country see conditions in Table 1 and MTA (WP1).

Table 1. Distribution and transport conditions for feed samples.

Analysis	Task	Amount	Container	Transport /Conservation until processing
Genomics (WP2)	2.3; 2.4	Extracted DNA from ≥11 g sample	Sterile tubes	Extracted DNA at -80°C
Bacteriology (WP2)	2.3	4 colonies from a subculture in Nutrient agar	Sterile tubes	Isolated colonies at -80°C
Trace elements (WP4)	4.7	More than 100 g	PET sterile bags, devoid of air	dark, cool place

4. Sample identifiers for feed samples

Austria			
Sample Reference	Description	Time points	Scheduled Month
AT20-Fe1	Austria, feed, sample 1	Once a year	Anytime within one year
AT20-Fe2	Austria, feed, sample 2		
AT20-Fe3	Austria, feed, sample 3		

Estonia			
Sample Reference	Description	Time points	Scheduled Month
EE20-Fe1	Estonia, feed, sample 1	Once a year	Anytime within one year
EE20-Fe2	Estonia, feed, sample 2		
EE20-Fe3	Estonia, feed, sample 3		

Czech Republic:			
Sample Reference	Description	Time points	Scheduled Month
CZ20-Fe1	Czech Republic, feed, sample 1	Once a year	Anytime within one year
CZ20-Fe2	Czech Republic, feed, sample 2		
CZ20-Fe3	Czech Republic, feed, sample 3		

Portugal			
Sample Reference	Description	Time points	Scheduled Month
PT20-Fe1	Portugal, feed, sample 1	Once a year	Anytime within one year
PT20-Fe2	Portugal, feed, sample 2		
PT20-Fe3	Portugal, feed, sample 3		

D. References

- Commission Regulation (EC) No 152/2009. (2009). Laying down the methods of sampling and analysis for the official control of feed. Official Journal of the European Union, L 54/1-L 54/130.
- EN ISO 6498:2012. (2012). Animal Feeding Stuffs – Guidelines for Sample Preparation. 2012.
- FAO. (2013). *Quality assurance for microbiology in feed analysis laboratories*, by R.A. Cowie. Edited by Harinder P.S. Makkar. FAO Animal Production and Health Manual No. 16. Rome.
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